

In the phytotron fertility was greatly reduced in plants at 38° / 27° C during flowering. Three heat-tolerant rices had higher fertility at 38° / 27° C. This was apparently not related to the fertility at 29° / 21° C, because the heat-susceptible line IR1561-228-3-3 had high fertility at this temperature. Heat-tolerant rices had more pollen grains per stigma than susceptible rices at both temperatures. In tolerant rices, high temperature had little

effect on the number of pollen grains per stigma. In susceptible rices, high temperature greatly reduced the number of pollen grains per stigma (see table).

Pollen shedding on the stigma in field-grown plants showed the same trend as in phytotron-grown plants. The amount of pollen shed on the stigma was not related to the number of pollen grains per anther; two tolerant rices, N22 and IET4658, had significantly less

pollen grains per anther than the other lines.

It appears that the amount of pollen shed on the stigma is related to the time of anther dehiscence in relation to filament elongation. This trait, which distinguishes heat-tolerant from heat-susceptible rices, is expressed under field conditions even in the absence of high temperature. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Rice bacterial blight status in the Punjab, India

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Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* has been known to occur in Punjab State of India since the 1940s. The disease, first observed in Gurdaspur district, was called *purarh* or *pansukh* in the local language, which means blighting or leaf-drying. It was considered to be due to some physiological disorder, and only in 1965 was its etiology established.

BB has been found to appear every year in varying degrees in different areas. During 1980 kharif (dry season), BB assumed an epiphytotic form and caused considerable yield loss throughout the state, in some areas as high as 60-70%. The kresak phase of the disease was also recorded in some fields for the first time.

Increase in BB incidence and severity may be attributed to higher nitrogen applications, very early transplanting, and conducive macro- and microclimatic conditions. The possibility of pathogenic variability also exists.

In the Punjab, the rice season lasts from May to October. Because almost all rice straw is burnt in the fields, there does not seem to be any chance for the bacterium to be carried over to the next crop season through infected rice straw. The possibility of pathogen survival in

Incidence of bacterial blight in Punjab, India.

Year	BB incidence
1975	Moderate to severe
1976	Low to severe
1977	Low to severe
1978	Low to severe
1979	Moderate to severe
1980	Severe

the stubble of infected plants is not ruled out, although harvested rice fields are immediately replanted to wheat.

The speculation is that BB bacterium carries over to the next crop season through infected seed. It is also possible that the pathogen survives in the rhizosphere of wheat and other nonhost plants during winter. Studies are being initiated to identify the source of carry-over. Studies on variability also are in progress. Some resistant donors have been identified and are being used in the breeding program. Progeny will be screened under artificial inoculation conditions. Attempts are being made to develop differentials and to test bacterial isolates from all over the state.

In vitro inhibition of rice fungal pathogens by extracts from higher plants

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Leaves of *Polyalthea longifolia*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, and *Cymbopogon* sp. were macerated. The aqueous

extracts were mixed at varying concentrations with potato dextrose agar and tested for antifungal activity by poison-food technique. Rhizomes of *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) and *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) were also tested for antifungal activity. Fungal pathogens tested were *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Sclerotium oryzae*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

Extracts from plants inhibited the growth of most fungal pathogens tested. The growth inhibition was greater in *R. solani* and *S. oryzae* than in other pathogens.

Extracts from *Azadirachta indica*, *Catharanthus roseus*, *Calotropis gigantea*, *Allium cepa*, *A. sativum*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, and *Clerodendron sp.* showed poor growth inhibition of the fungal pathogens tested. ■

Nilaparvata bakeri transmission of rice ragged stunt virus

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Rice ragged stunt virus transmission abilities of *Nephotettix virescens*, *Recilia dorsalis*, *Sogatella furcifera*, and *Nilaparvata bakeri* were tested. Nymphs of *N. virescens* and adults of *R. dorsalis*

and *S. furcifera* were allowed feeding access on diseased rice plants for one day. Each insect was tested for transmission ability by serial daily transfers onto a test plant, Taichung Native 1, in a test tube.

Nilaparvata bakeri nymphs were

allowed feeding access on diseased rice plants for 17 hours (overnight), and were reared on a host, *Leersia hexandra*, for 7 days (incubation period). Transmission ability was tested by alternately putting the insect for 16 hours on a test rice plant and 8 hours on *Leersia hex-*

andra. *N. bakeri* would die if fed only on rice plants.

N. virescens, *R. dorsalis*, and *S. furcifera* did not transmit rice ragged stunt virus but *N. bakeri* did. ■

Resistance of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, the rice bacterial blight pathogen, to phenazine

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The bacteriostatic effect of phenazine on *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, the

rice bacterial blight pathogen, under laboratory conditions was confirmed.

Phenazine-resistant variants of the bacterial strains were easily obtained by the paper disc method on peptone sucrose agar plates (Table 1). The number of phenazine-resistant variants was not correlated with virulence. Variants derived from strains of pv. *oryzae* that had lost their virulence seemed to

be more virulent to RD1, a susceptible rice cultivar than the parent strains. Some variants obtained from other virulent strains were similar to and others different from parental strains.

Two days after RD1 was inoculated with both wild type parental strains and variants derived from them, derivative variants produced longer lesions than parental strains (Table 2). Variants derived from different groups appeared to increase in virulence in most strains tested, but only a few were similar to the parental strains.

Since it is relatively easy to obtain the phenazine-resistant variants, the efficiency of the chemical *in vitro* should be monitored before a recommendation is made under field conditions. ■

Electron microscopy of particles of rice tungro virus complex

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Rice plants infected with ragged stunt virus at IRRI were homogenized in Turin. Two types of particles, apparently those of rice tungro virus complex, were found by electron microscopy, in addition to particles of ragged stunt virus, indicating that the diseased plants were multiple infected (IRRN 3[2]:9, 1978).

The viruses were purified from the sap of the infected plants using Freon, Nonidet P40, ultracentrifugation through sucrose cushions, and density gradient centrifugation in cesium sulfate. After negative staining, the preparation was examined under an electron microscope whose magnification was calibrated with a diffraction grating replica.

Table 1. Inhibition effect of phenazine on strains of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* and phenazine-resistant variants from the inhibition zone. Bangkok, Thailand.

Strain	Virulence group	Inhibition zone ^a (cm)	Colony variants ^a (no.)
TB7535	0	6.6	2.6
TB7612	0	5.5	0.2
TB7618	0	4.2	22.7
TB7803	0	6.2	124.7
TB7811	0	6.1	0.7
TB7817	0	8.1	4.8
TB7824	0	8.4	5.1
TB7615	I	5.4	43.7
TB7804	I	4.5	31.3
TB7810	I	5.0	5.1
TB7837	I	8.5	187.9
TB7212	II	7.5	28.8
TB7536	II	6.1	1.9
TB7805	II	4.2	6.3
TB7834	II	7.7	79.6

^aMean of 9 plates.

Table 2. Effect of phenazine application on bacterial blight of RD1 caused by wild type parental strains and phenazine-resistant variants Bangkok, Thailand.

Strain	Lesion ^a (cm)			
	Phenazine treated		Check	
	Wild type	Variant	Wild type	Variant
TB7535	0.9	5.9	1.4	5.8
TB7672	0.3	7.6	1.0	2.1
TB7678	1.8	27.5	3.4	24.4
TB7803	1.5	28.0	3.4	26.0
TB7811	0.6	13.4	5.9	20.9
TB7817	1.1	17.8	5.0	22.6
TB7824	0.2	0.8	3.5	9.0
TB7615	3.0	23.5	12.1	24.2
TB7804	0.9	23.3	8.7	27.5
TB7810	10.3	13.2	11.3	22.5
TB7837	1.1	22.8	26.2	29.3
TB7212	0.2	17.1	17.9	22.5
TB7536	16.5	16.9	27.9	29.9
TB7895	20.4	22.5	24.8	25.7
TB7834	1.2	23.9	27.1	26.8

^aMean of 3 replications.